

FINAL REPORT

1 General Information

DFG reference number: SCHU 1369/24-2

Project number: 275255277

Project title: Influence of hydrogen and oxygen on the initial steps of soot formation

Names of the applicant: Prof. Dr. Christof Schulz

Official address: Institut für Energie- und Material-Prozesse-Reaktive Fluide (EMPI-RF), Universität Duisburg-Essen Carl-Benz-Straße 199 47057 Duisburg

Reporting period (entire funding period): 01.01.2020–31.12.2024

2 Summary

Driven by the need to reduce soot formation in practical combustion processes on the one side and the interest in targeted synthesis of 'carbon black' on the other side, the process of soot formation has been continuously studied for decades. In practical combustion processes, one possibility to influence soot formation is related to the admixing of additives to the fuel or the use of fuel blends. One possible fuel compound is molecular hydrogen. H_2 is expected to have a strong impact on soot formation: The equilibrium process $RH + H = R + H_2$, where RH is a hydrocarbon and R the corresponding hydrocarbonyl radical, is the basis of the HACA (hydrogen-abstraction, carbon addition) mechanism that is often used for describing soot chemistry [1]. Molecular oxygen can also be regarded as a soot-suppressing compound since increasing the amount of O_2 in a hydrocarbon system logically reduces the amount of condensed carbon and enhances the secondary oxidation. In addition, fuel-bonded oxygen is supposed to have an influence on soot formation. Studying the influence of oxygenated fuels on soot formation has a high relevance due to growing interest in the use of liquid oxygenated fuels derived from biomass [2].

The objectives of the second phase of this project were to study the effect of fuel additives, focusing on the impact of fuel structure—particularly chemically bonded oxygen—and the introduction of molecular H_2 and O_2 on the initial stages of carbon particle formation. Special attention was given to fuel-dependent reaction pathways involved in the formation of the first particles, the chemistry of particle growth, and the effects on the structure and morphology of the final particles.

Progress report

In carbon-particle formation from hydrocarbons, hydrogen and oxygen play an important role. The influence of molecular and bonded oxygen on particle induction times, particle formation rates, particle volume fractions, as well as on reaction channels leading to soot was studied using a close interaction of experiments and modeling. Methane, ethylene, and benzene were studied as typical representatives of systematically different hydrocarbon classes.

The general outline of this project is to study the reaction of selected hydrocarbons (CH_4 , C_2H_4 , and C_6H_6) in the presence of oxygenated species classes, i.e., cyclic ethers (furans and tetrahydrofurans), as well as alcohols by combining complementary reaction environments, such as shock tubes, and a McKenna burner.

To fulfill these objectives, shock-tube experiments were used as they enable quasi-instantaneous heating of the fuel precursors and provide kinetics information of the initial reaction steps with very high time resolution, flow-reactor experiments enabled the investigation of slower subsequent process such as the initial particle formation and its interaction with the environment for pyrolytic and oxidative (McKenna burner) conditions. The experiments facilities were located mainly in Duisburg (Professor Schulz, Institute for Energy and Material Processes – Reactive Fluids, University of Duisburg-Essen). A close collaboration with Professor Eremin (as Mercator Fellow) and his entire team at the Joint Institute for High Temperatures (IHT) of the Russian Academy of Science in Moscow was anticipated with the frame of this project but needed to be interrupted in the progress of the project for political reasons outside our control.

Effect of oxygenates on soot formation from methane oxidation and pyrolysis in shock tube

Oxidation: The oxidation of fuel-rich CH₄ mixtures ($\phi = 5$) and the impact of three oxygenated additives – diethyl ether (DEE), methanol, and dimethoxymethane (DMM) – on soot formation were investigated in shock-tube experiments at 1480–1900 K and ~5 bar. Temperature and CO concentrations were measured using infrared (IR) absorption (P8, R21). Soot formation was analyzed using laser extinction measurements. The objective was to investigate soot promoting/suppressing capabilities of these fuel additives by measuring the soot bell-shaped curves. The temperature is an important kinetic parameter for soot formation. These parameters and measured CO profiles provide experimental data to check the predictions of the chemical models. Figure 1 shows the experimental setup that was used for the measurement of soot extinction, CO concentration and temperature. Since two-line thermometry was applied throughout the project for all fuels and additives, a brief description is provided below:

Based on the Beer-Lambert law, the relationship between incident beam intensity and transmitted beam intensity can be expressed as (Eq. (1)),

$$(I/I_0)_\nu = \exp(-pS(T)lx\phi(\nu)) \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

with p is the pressure, $S(T)$ is the line strength at a certain temperature, l is the inner diameter of the shock tube and thus the absorption length, x is the species mole fraction, $\phi(\nu)$ is the absorption line shape that is assumed here to follow a Voigt function. The ratio $R(T)$ of the peak absorbance at the line center of both transitions is only a function of the temperature and can be calculated according to Eq. (2):

$$T(R) = \left[\ln \frac{R(T) k_B}{R(T_0) hc} \frac{1}{E''_2 - E''_1} + \frac{1}{T_0} \right]^{-1} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

Figure 1: Schematics of the laser absorption (purple line) and the laser-extinction setup (red line).

T_0 is the reference temperature (296 K), E'' is the lower-state energy of the transition, h , c , and k_B are the Planck constant, speed of light, and the Boltzmann constant, respectively. The line strengths of the P8 and R21 lines are taken from the HITEMP database [3]. Collisional broadening coefficients were taken from Ren et al. [4, 5]. Temperature and CO concentration profiles were calculated in an iterative way as described in Refs. [4, 6]. Experimental results were compared to five detailed kinetics models (Yasunaga et al. [7], Aramco3.0 [8], Fikri et al. [9], Jacobs et al. [10], modified CRECK [11]). Figure 2 shows exemplary the temperature and CO profiles for methane oxidation at different temperatures and $\phi = 5$.

Figure 2: Temperature and CO concentration profiles for methane oxidation at $\phi = 5$. All measurements are compared with simulations. Lines are results of the simulations.

Modeling of the optical density: Simulations of optical density were performed with the detailed kinetics mechanism of Nobili et al. [11] complemented by the decomposition and H-abstraction reactions for DEE [7] and DMM [12]. Large polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and soot are represented by 25 different BINs ($C_{20}H_5 - C_{320000000}H_{95999999}$). All BINs were considered as soot from which the mass fraction of soot was calculated. The soot optical density was calculated according to Eq. (3).

$$\ln(I/I_0) = -f_V L 6 \pi E(m)/\lambda$$

with I and I_0 as the transmitted and incident laser intensity, f_V is the soot volume fraction, which is calculated from the soot mass fraction, L is the path length (i.e., the shock-tube diameter), and λ is the laser wavelength (633 nm). The absorption function of soot is $E(m) = -\text{Im}[(m^2 - 1)/(m^2 + 2)]$. The soot density for the calculation of f_V was assumed to be 2 g/cm^3 [13] and $E(m)$ was set to 0.31 [14].

DMM reduced the soot yield, DEE increased it, and methanol had a minor effect. All additives shifted soot formation to lower temperatures due to earlier ignition, as seen in CO and temperature measurements. Simulations with the modified Nobili et al. [20] mechanism accurately predicted soot peak volume fractions and additive effects. Figure 3 (top) shows the temperature-dependent optical density for methane with additives at $\phi = 5$.

Pyrolysis: In the same manner as for the oxidation the pyrolysis of methane and methane with additives was determined. A soot reducing effect of DMM on the soot yield was also observed on the pyrolysis plot in figure 3 (down) with a 20 % decrease of the soot yield at the maximum compared to the reference mixture. The simulation of the pyrolysis results is also in good agreement with the experimental results except a shift of about 200 K towards lower temperatures of the simulations. A very good prediction of the soot reducing effect of DMM is

Figure 3: measured and simulated optical density of methane with additives for oxidation and pyrolysis.

observed. The results were presented and published in Proceedings of Combustion Institute [15] and in the European Combustion Meeting 2023.

Effect of oxygenates on soot formation from gasoline surrogate pyrolysis in shock tube

The impact of methanol and butanol on soot formation during the pyrolysis of a toluene primary reference fuel mixture (TPRF91) with a research octane number (RON) of 91 was examined with shock-tube experiments. The TPRF91 mixture consisted of 17 mol% n-heptane, 29 mol% iso-octane, and 54 mol% toluene. To evaluate the individual contributions of these fuel components to soot formation during TPRF91 pyrolysis, the pyrolysis of argon-diluted mixtures of (1) toluene, (2) iso-octane, and (3) n-heptane was also analyzed. Additionally, to facilitate the interpretation of the TPRF91 + methanol and TPRF91 + butanol experiments, the effects of both alcohols on soot formation during the thermal decomposition of toluene and iso-octane were investigated in a separate set of measurements. Pyrolysis was monitored behind reflected shock waves at pressures between 2.1 and 4.2 bar and in the temperature range of 2060–2815 K. Laser extinction at 633 nm was used to determine the soot yield as a function of reaction time. In addition, temperature measurements were also elaborated using the same set-up as in figure 1. It was found that the thermal decomposition of toluene is the main soot source of TPRF91.

Figure 4: Comparison between measured and simulated optical densities $D_{633\text{ nm}}$ at $t = 0.4$ ms. Symbols and lines are experimental and simulated results, respectively.

Figure 4 presents a summary and comparison between the reference mixture TPRF91 and its individual components – toluene, iso-octane, and n-heptane. Both experimental data and simulations indicate that soot particles are predominantly formed during the pyrolysis of toluene. At higher temperatures, the soot production from TPRF91 pyrolysis closely resembles that of pure toluene, despite TPRF91 containing only 54 mol% toluene. The CRECK mechanism quantitatively deviates from experimental results in terms of maximum soot concentrations. These discrepancies are likely due to uncertainties in the high-temperature gas-phase chemistry of toluene decomposition. Enhancing the accuracy of the high-temperature toluene chemistry in the model could therefore lead to improved simulation results. Figure 5 presents optical densities measured during the pyrolysis of TRF91 mixtures with addition of methanol and n-butanol. A slight decrease of optical densities is observed in Mix 1b (methanol) compared to mix 1a (TRF91), and a slight shift toward higher temperatures is noticed for Mix 1c (n-butanol). These observations are relatively well captured by the simulations. The results were published in The journal of physical chemistry A [16].

Figure 5: Measured and simulated optical density $D_{633\text{ nm}}$ at $t = 0.4\text{ ms}$ for TPRF91, TPRF91 + CH_3OH , and TPRF91 + $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$. Symbols and lines are experimental and simulated results, respectively.

Effect of oxygenates on soot formation from ethylene in shock tube

The impact of various oxygenated co-reactants on soot formation was also investigated by analyzing the pyrolysis of gas mixtures using ethylene as the base fuel. Selected oxygenated co-reactants included aliphatic alcohols (methanol, ethanol, and n-butanol) and linear ethers (diethyl ether, dimethoxymethane) and cyclic ethers (furan, and tetrahydrofuran). The pyrolysis experiments were conducted behind reflected shock waves at approximately 3 bar. Soot inception times and optical densities were measured over time using laser extinction at 633 nm. Simultaneously, the temperature evolution was monitored using time-resolved two-color CO absorption spectroscopy with quantum-cascade lasers operating at 4.73 and 4.56 μm . The temperature is an additional validation target for the model predictions. Soot particle sizes were assessed using time-resolved laser-induced incandescence with a 1064 nm Nd:YAG laser. A key finding was that, among the tested co-reactants, only methanol did not promote soot formation when using ethylene as the soot precursor. In contrast, all other oxygenated additives led to increased soot production. Measured temperatures were compared with simulations using a detailed chemical kinetics mechanism developed by Pepichestakul et al. [17]. Further kinetics modeling of hydrocarbon pyrolysis, PAH (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon) formation, and soot growth was performed using both the CRECK mechanism and a combined mechanism incorporating the CRECK model with a PAH sub-mechanism of Sun et al. [18]. The simulations suggest that the enhanced soot formation in the presence of oxygenated co-reactants is driven by the thermal decomposition of these species, which releases CH_3 and C_3H_3 radicals that accelerate the formation of benzene C_6H_6 rings. Figure 6 represents the optical density measurements for all

Figure 6: Measured optical density $D_{633\text{ nm}}$ at $t_r = 1.5\text{ ms}$. Dashed lines are non-linear curve-fit functions to guide the eye.

tested mixtures as a function of temperature at a fixed reaction time of 1.5 ms. To better illustrate the influence of various additives, each panel compares a specific group of oxygenates against the reference mixture (Ref-Mix: ethylene at the corresponding concentration). Panels figure 6a and 6b display results for mixtures containing 0.5 mol% oxygenated additives. With the exception of Met-0.5, all mixtures exhibit a soot-promoting effect relative to Ref-Mix. Notably, the Furan-0.5 mixture produces a significantly broader soot yield profile than the other additives. Panel figure 6c highlights the impact of additive concentration on soot formation, comparing mixtures with 0.5 % and 1.0 % of either CH₃OH or DMM. Increasing the CH₃OH concentration to 1.0 % enhances its soot-suppressing effect slightly compared to the 0.5% mixture. This concentration-dependent trend is less pronounced in the case of DMM.

Modeling results: Pyrene (C₁₆H₁₀) is a key polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) often regarded as a representative marker for soot nucleation. Figure 7 shows the main kinetics pathways of C₁₆H₁₀ formation in C₂H₄ pyrolysis. A critical step in PAH growth is the formation of the first aromatic ring, with propargyl recombination to benzene identified as the dominant mechanism under the conditions of this study. Although the reaction between diacetylene C₄H₂ and acetylene C₂H₂ contributes to benzene formation, its role is comparatively minor. However, C₄H₂ becomes more significant in subsequent steps, particularly in the formation of naphthyl species C₁₀H₇.

Propargyl radicals C₃H₃ themselves can originate from the interaction of methyl radicals (CH₃) with acetylene through various reaction pathways, denoted as (1a), (1b), and (1c):

Figure 7: Main kinetics pathways of C₁₆H₁₀ formation in C₂H₄ pyrolysis. Dotted arrows are hydrogen-abstraction reactions. Solid arrows involve acetylene as reactant.

Consequently, in the early stages of PAH development, the presence of C₃H₃ and CH₃ radicals is crucial. Atomic hydrogen also plays a key role, actively participating in numerous intermediate hydrogen abstraction reactions. The results were presented and published in Proceedings of Combustion Institute [19].

Effect of oxygenates on soot formation from benzene in shock tube

The effect of adding oxygenated hydrocarbons, namely methanol, ethanol, and n-butanol and ethers such as diethyl ether, dimethoxymethane, furan, and tetrahydrofuran on soot formation during benzene pyrolysis was investigated. Experiments were conducted behind reflected shock waves at pressures around 1.4 bar and within a temperature range of 1670–2680 K. Soot optical densities and soot-inception times were determined by laser extinction measurements at 633 nm. For these measurements, the gas mixtures contained 2.00 mol% benzene (C₆H₆) and 0.75 mol% additive, with argon as the diluent. Figure 8 shows optical-density results of all investigated mixtures as a function of temperature at a reaction time of 0.7 ms. It is separated in three parts for a better visualization of the effect of the different additives and each sub-figure compares, under the same y-axis scale, a group of additives with Mix 1. First of all,

a noticeable decrease of the soot yield with all the additive mixtures compared to the reference mixture is observed.

Figure 8: Comparison between the optical density $D_{633\text{nm}}$ measured at $t = 0.7$ ms of Mix 1 with, a) Mix 2b, Mix 3, and Mix 4; b) Mix 5 and Mix 6; c) Mix 7 and Mix 8. Dashed lines are non-linear curve fits (peak function) to guide the eye.

The optical densities shown in previous figures are normalized to the total carbon content of the mixture (including the amount present in the additive). Thus, for comparing the chemical effect of the oxygenates, we better compare the absorbance related to a fixed concentration of benzene as presented in figure 9. One can observe the “direct” effect of the additive of soot production compared to the reference mixture. We notice that the furan mixture as additive produces more soot than Mix 1 (C_6H_6) and that DEE and DMM addition show the best soot-reducing effect compared to all other additives. THF and $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH}$ mixtures also result in similar soot reducing effects.

Figure 9: Comparison between the absorbance $\ln(I_0/I)$, measured at $t = 0.7$ ms of Mix 1 with mixtures Mix 2b and Mix 3 to Mix 8. Dashed lines are non-linear curve fits (peak function) to guide the eye.

Given the high reactant concentrations used in the shock tube, the system cannot be considered isothermal, and soot nucleation times exhibit strong temperature dependence. Therefore, temperature profiles were measured over time using two-color infrared absorption of CO with two quantum-cascade lasers operating at different wavelengths. To facilitate these measurements, 0.80 mol% CO was introduced as the target species for thermometry, and 5.00 mol% helium was added to enhance vibrational relaxation.

Both the temperature data and measured optical densities were compared to numerical simulations based on a detailed chemical kinetics mechanism developed by the CRECK Modeling Group. Further simulations using an updated mechanism, combining the CRECK model

(Pejpichestakul et al. [17]) with a recent PAH sub-mechanism of Sun et al. [20] showed significantly improved agreement with experimental optical density results, underscoring the importance of PAH chemistry in modeling soot formation. The results were published in *Combustion and flame* [24].

Figure 10: Measured temperature in the mixtures: a) Mix 1, b) Mix 4, c) Mix 8, and d) Mix 6. Short-dashed lines in a) and b) represent simulations based on the CRECK mechanism [21]. Dashed lines in c) are simulations based on the same mechanism modified with the THF sub-model from Tripathi et al. [22]. d): Simulations based on the CRECK mechanism modified with the DMM reactions from Jacobs et al. [10] (dotted), Sun et al. [20] (short dashed), and Marrodán et al. [23] (dashed).

Effect of DME addition in premixed ethylene/air flame

The effect of DME in a standard premixed ethylene/air flame was investigated. Both experimental measurements and computational analysis of soot formation in a standard premixed ethylene/air flame with incremental additions of dimethyl ether (DME), ranging from 15 % to 100 %. Soot volume fractions were quantified using the laser light extinction method at a wavelength of 520 nm. Flame temperature profiles as a function of height above the burner were recorded using standard Pt-Rh thermocouples. Experimental results revealed that introducing 15 % DME into the ethylene/air flame led to a 20 % increase in soot volume fraction. However, replacing 60% of ethylene with DME resulted in a fivefold reduction in soot volume fraction compared to the baseline ethylene/air flame. Kinetic modeling of soot formation as a function of burner height was performed using detailed chemical mechanisms developed by the CRECK Modeling Group (<http://creckmodeling.chem.polimi.it/>).

Figure 11 presents photographic images of the investigated flames. In these images, the blue region represents the main oxidation zone (MOZ), where the primary chemical reactions responsible for fuel decomposition occur. This is followed by the particle formation zone, where soot precursors are generated, and subsequently by the yellow-luminous region of the flame, where soot particles form and grow.

The addition of DME has a notable impact on the MOZ. With 15 % DME addition, no visible changes to the MOZ are apparent. However, a slight increase in the brightness of the yellow zone can be observed compared to the pure ethylene/air flame. In both of these flames, the MOZ appears as a narrow disc, and the flame image is dominated by the yellow luminosity of the post-flame gases.

Figure 11: Changes in the structure of the C_2H_4 /air flames with different additions of DME.

As the DME content increases to 45 %, the MOZ expands significantly. At 75 % DME addition, the MOZ extends to nearly half the total visible flame height, while the yellow glow, indicative of soot formation, is only faintly visible, suggesting a substantial reduction in soot production. With 90 % DME addition, and in the pure DME/air flame, no visible soot can be observed, indicating near-complete suppression of soot formation at these conditions.

Based on the experimental and simulation results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Substituting up to 15 % of ethylene with dimethyl ether (DME) in a premixed ethylene/air flame increases the soot volume fraction by approximately 20%. However, replacing 30–60% of ethylene with DME reduces the soot volume fraction from 0.2 ppm to 0.01 ppm – over an order of magnitude decrease.
- Kinetics modeling using CRECK mechanisms for hydrocarbon pyrolysis and oxidation, including oxygenated species like DME, showed good agreement with experimental data when soot volume fractions exceeded 0.01 ppm. The observed reduction of soot with higher DME content is primarily attributed to changes in soot formation kinetics rather than alterations in the flame temperature profile.
- Kinetics analysis indicates that the initial increase in soot with ~15 % DME is due to enhanced formation of propyne (C_3H_{4-p}) from CH_3 and acetylene, followed by its conversion to propargyl C_3H_3 and then benzene C_6H_6 .

These findings provide valuable data for the development and validation of soot formation kinetic models in flames involving oxygenated additives like DME. The results were published in Combustion and Flame [25].

3 Published project results

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

- [1] D. Nativel, J. Herzler, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, Effect of oxygenates on fuel-rich oxidation of CH_4 : Shock-tube analysis with extinction, CO-concentration, and temperature measurements, Proc. Combust. Inst. 40 (2024) 105253.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2024.105253>.

- [2] D. Nativel, C. Shao, S.P. Cooper, E.L. Petersen, C. Schulz, M. Fikri, S. Peukert, Impact of methanol and butanol on soot formation in gasoline surrogate pyrolysis: A shock-tube study, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 127 (2023) 1259-1270. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.2c06599>.
- [3] D. Nativel, S. Peukert, J. Herzler, A. Drakon, M. Korshunova, E. Mikheyeva, A. Eremin, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, Shock-tube study on the influence of oxygenated co-reactants on ethylene decomposition under pyrolytic conditions *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 39 (2023) 1099-1108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2022.07.209>
- [4] D. Nativel, J. Herzler, S. Krzywdziak, S. Peukert, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, Shock-tube study of the influence of oxygenated additives on benzene pyrolysis: Measurement of optical densities, soot inception times and comparison with simulations, *Combust. Flame* 243 (2022) 111985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2022.111985>.
- [5] A.V. Drakon, E.V. Gurentsov, A.V. Eremin, R.N. Kolotushkin, E.S. Khodyko, H. Jander, Special features of soot formation in a standard premixed ethylene/air flame diluted with DME, *Combust. Flame* 246 (2022) 112309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2022.112309>.

4.2 Other publications and published results

J. Herzler, D. Nativel, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, Shock-tube study of the pyrolysis and oxidation of fuel-rich CH₄ and CH₄/oxygenated-additive mixtures in the context of polygeneration: Soot optical density, CO-concentration and temperature measurements, 11th ECM 2023, Rouen, France.

J. Herzler, D. Nativel, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, The effect of oxygenated species on the pyrolysis and the fuel-rich oxidation of CH₄ in the context of polygeneration: Extinction, CO-concentration and temperature measurements, 29th ICDERS 2023, Siheung, Korea

J. Herzler, D. Nativel, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, Shock-tube study of CH₄ and CH₄/diethyl ether mixtures in the context of polygeneration processes: Extinction, CO concentration and temperature measurements at moderate pressure, 10th ECM 2021, Naples, Italy

4 Further information on the project, qualifications and outlook

The project 427458221 was carried out at the University of Duisburg-Essen at the Institute for Energy and Material Processes – Reactive Fluids by Atheer Attallah Sallom and Dr. Sebastian Peukert under the scientific direction of Prof. Dr. Christof Schulz with strong scientific support from Dr. Fikri and Dr. Herzler.

An essential component of this research project involved collaborating Professor Eremin (as Mercator Fellow) and his entire team at the Joint Institute for High Temperatures (IHT) of the Russian Academy of Science in Moscow. Unfortunately, the project timeline overlapped with the COVID-19 pandemic and Russia-Ukraine conflict, causing delays in some parts of the work program. Additionally, the University of Duisburg-Essen experienced significant disruptions due to a cyberattack, which further hindered project progress and prevented the ordering of replacement experimental equipment that failed. We have notified the German Research Foundation and have obtained approval to extend the project duration.

The planned activity with burnt-gas flow reactor could not be completed due to the travel restrictions of researchers from Russia. Despite all, the project yielded fruitful outcomes, culminating in the publication of four archival papers.

References

- [1] M. Frenklach, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 4 (2002) 2028-2037. 10.1039/B110045A.
- [2] K. Kohse-Höinghaus, P. Osswald, T.A. Cool, T. Kasper, N. Hansen, F. Qi, C.K. Westbrook, P.R. Westmoreland, *Angewandte Chemie-International Edition* 49 (2010) 3572-3597. 10.1002/anie.200905335.
- [3] L.S. Rothman, I.E. Gordon, R.J. Barber, H. Dothe, R.R. Gamache, A. Goldman, V.I. Perevalov, S.A. Tashkun, J. Tennyson, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Rad. Transf.* 111 (2010) 2139-2150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2010.05.001>.
- [4] D. He, D. Nativel, J. Herzler, J.B. Jeffries, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, *Appl. Phys. B* 126 (2020) 142. 10.1007/s00340-020-07492-7.
- [5] W. Ren, A. Farooq, D.F. Davidson, R.K. Hanson, *Appl. Phys. B* 107 (2012) 849-860. 10.1007/s00340-012-5046-1.
- [6] D. He, L. Shi, D. Nativel, J. Herzler, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, *Combust. Flame* 216 (2020) 194-205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2020.02.024>.
- [7] K. Yasunaga, J.M. Simmie, H.J. Curran, T. Koike, O. Takahashi, Y. Kuraguchi, Y. Hidaka, *Combust. Flame* 158 (2011) 1032-1036. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2010.10.012>.
- [8] C.-W. Zhou, Y. Li, U. Burke, C. Banyon, K.P. Somers, S. Ding, S. Khan, J.W. Hargis, T. Sikes, O. Mathieu, E.L. Petersen, M. AlAbbad, A. Farooq, Y. Pan, Y. Zhang, Z. Huang, J. Lopez, Z. Loparo, S.S. Vasu, H.J. Curran, *Combust. Flame* 197 (2018) 423-438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2018.08.006>.
- [9] M. Fikri, Y. Sakai, J. Herzler, C. Schulz, *Proceedings of the 26th International Colloquium on the Dynamics of Explosions and Reactive Systems* (2017) Paper Nr. 957.
- [10] S. Jacobs, M. Döntgen, A.B.S. Alquaity, W.A. Kopp, L.C. Kröger, U. Burke, H. Pitsch, K. Leonhard, H.J. Curran, K.A. Heufer, *Combust. Flame* 205 (2019) 522-533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2018.12.026>.
- [11] A. Nobili, A. Cuoci, W. Pejpichestakul, M. Pelucchi, C. Cavallotti, T. Faravelli, *Combust. Flame* 243 (2022) 112073. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2022.112073>.
- [12] L. Marrodán, M. Fabiola, M. Ángela, B. Rafael, M.U. and Alzueta, *Combust. Sci. Technol.* 188 (2016) 719-729. 10.1080/00102202.2016.1138826.
- [13] H.A. Michelsen, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 38 (2021) 1197-1205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2020.06.383>.
- [14] S.A. Skeen, K. Yasutomi, E. Cenker, B. Adamson, N. Hansen, L.M. Pickett, *SAE Int. J. Engines* 11 (2018) 805-816.
- [15] D. Nativel, J. Herzler, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 40 (2024) 105253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2024.105253>.
- [16] D. Nativel, C. Shao, S.P. Cooper, E.L. Petersen, C. Schulz, M. Fikri, S. Peukert, *J. Phys. Chem. A* 127 (2023) 1259-1270. 10.1021/acs.jpca.2c06599.
- [17] W. Pejpichestakul, E. Ranzi, M. Pelucchi, A. Frassoldati, A. Cuoci, A. Parente, T. Faravelli, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 37 (2019) 1013-1021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2018.06.104>.
- [18] W. Sun, A. Hamadi, S. Abid, N. Chaumeix, A. Comandini, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 38 (2021) 891-900. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2020.06.077>.
- [19] D. Nativel, S. Peukert, J. Herzler, A. Drakon, M. Korshunova, E. Mikheyeva, A. Eremin, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 39 (2023) 1099-1108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2022.07.209>.
- [20] W. Sun, T. Tao, M. Lailliau, N. Hansen, B. Yang, P. Dagaut, *Combust. Flame* 193 (2018) 491-501. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2018.04.008>.
- [21] W. Pejpichestakul, E. Ranzi, M. Pelucchi, A. Frassoldati, A. Cuoci, A. Parente, T. Faravelli, *Proc. Comb. Inst.* 37 (2019) 1013-1021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2018.06.104>.
- [22] R. Tripathi, C. Lee, R.X. Fernandes, H. Olivier, H.J. Curran, S. Mani Sarathy, H. Pitsch, *Proc. Comb. Inst.* 36 (2017) 587-595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2016.07.103>.
- [23] L. Marrodán, E. Royo, Á. Millera, R. Bilbao, M.U. Alzueta, *Energy Fuels* 29 (2015) 3507-3517. 10.1021/acs.energyfuels.5b00459.

- [24] D. Nativel, J. Herzler, S. Krzywdziak, S. Peukert, M. Fikri, C. Schulz, *Combust. Flame* 243 (2022) 111985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2022.111985>.
- [25] A.V. Drakon, E.V. Gurentsov, A.V. Eremin, R.N. Kolotushkin, E.S. Khodyko, H. Jander, *Combust. Flame* 246 (2022) 112309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2022.112309>.